
Influential Factors in Parents' Perception of Juvenile Weight Status

Jonathan G. Aragon

Abstract

The goal of this study was to identify what socio-demographic and anthropometric factors influence parents' perception of their child's weight status. While previous studies concur on the perpetual failure of guardians' ability to identify their children's weight status accurately, few research studies have identified the source of these failures. Hence, using a random digit-dialing methodology, data was collected from 293 White and Hispanic/Latino birth mothers and fathers in eastern Riverside County, California. Data was analyzed for six predictor variables using sequential binary logistic regression analysis. Findings indicated that Hispanic/Latinos are 3 times more likely to identify their child as "overweight" as compared to Whites. Results suggest that actual child's weight status and parents' ethnicity have the greatest influence on parental perception of juvenile weight status.

Introduction

Unhealthy adiposity in youth is an important public health issue. Such a condition in one's developing years has both immediate and long-term physical, physiological psychological, and social consequences. The U.S. Department of Health and Human Service's Healthy People 2020 has designated "Obesity in Children and Adolescents" as a leading health indicator and has set Nutrition and Weight Status (NWS) objective 10, "Reduce the proportion of children and adolescents who are considered obese," and NWS-11, "Prevent inappropriate weight gain in youth and adults," as measurable objectives for nationwide health improvement (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services [FHHS], 2012). National survey analysis from 2009-2010 revealed 17% of American juveniles aged 2-19 to be obese (Ogden, Carroll, Kit, & Flegal, 2012), indicating a 22% increase in prevalence since the 1999-2000 survey (HHS, 2013). Certain U.S. regions have higher rates of childhood obesity as compared to the national prevalence rates. For example, in eastern Riverside County, California, an astonishing one third (29.5%) of children aged 2-17 are obese; overweight and obese children combined make up 42% of this region's child population (Health Assessment Resource Center, 2011).

Eastern Riverside County has been historically neglected in health assessments. To address this, the Health

Assessment Resource Center conducts a triennial health assessment in order to identify key health issues in the region. The Center's 2010 Executive Report of survey findings noted that 82% of this region's parents stated they perceived their children to be "about the right weight" in contrast to the actual 42% child overweight and obesity rates (Health Assessment Resource Center, 2011).

These findings highlight a parental inability to accurately identify their children's weight. Parents' misperception of their children's weight status is a well-documented issue which is not isolated to the eastern Riverside County region. Previous scientific studies, utilizing an array of research methodology, demonstrate parents' failure in identifying their children's accurate weight status (see the Appendix for "weight status"). Regardless of the methods used, guardians have a proven lack of proficiency in accurately reporting their child's weight status in comparison to actual body composition measurements (Hernandez, 2005; Hernandez, Cheng, & Serwint, 2010; Parry, Netuveli, Parry, & Saxena, 2008; Vuorela, Saha, & Salo, 2010).

Research into the sources of such misclassification is important in regard to its implication for prevention programming and health-related parenting decisions; however, few research studies have attempted to identify causes of these weight-perception failures. Two relevant published studies explored this phenomenon in the past couple of years. Chapan-o, Langellier, Kim, and Whaley (2011) found that maternal BMI and child's birth weight are associated with misperceptions of child weight status. Another study indicated parental weight status and the child's age and gender were the most prevailing socio-demographic and anthropometric (see the Appendix for "anthropometric") influences on parents' perception of juvenile weight status (Hudson, McGloin, & McConnon, 2012). Although insightful and informative, the study by Hudson and colleagues (2012) was completed in Ireland and is not representative of the region in the current study. Hence, this study proposes to examine parental perceptions in the eastern Riverside County, California population.

The goal of this study is to identify what socio-demographic and anthropometric factors correlate with parents' perceptual outcome of their child's weight status. Parents' perceptions of their child's weight status can be

derived from their self-reported observations. It is posited that significant predictors will be parallel to the findings of Hudson et al. (2012).

Method

The Health Assessment Resource Center administers triennial regional health assessments via the Community Health Monitor survey. The goal of the survey is to assess the health and well-being of eastern Riverside County residents. Survey data was collected via random digit-dialed samples from landline and cellular telephones in both English and Spanish amid the months of January and March, 2010. Respondents were limited to adults 18 years of age and older. There were two separate surveys administered, one to assess adult residents and another for their children. The surveys were designed to model the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention's Behavioral Risk Factor Surveillance System instrument (Health Assessment Resource Center, 2011). The child survey requested adult respondents to select a random child living in the home and then answer questions related to the child's health and well-being. This study selected a sample ($n = 293$) of White (45%) and Hispanic/ Latino (55%) birth mothers and fathers of children aged 1-17 years from the Community Health Monitor 2010 child survey results for analysis. Demographics of the respondents' children were 59% male and 41% female, and the average age was 10 years old (see Tables 1-8).

The outcome variable (parents' perception of child weight status) was constructed from the survey question "Do you consider your child to be overweight, underweight, or about the right weight?" Because of the low number of respondents reporting underweight, this question was coded as a dichotomous outcome variable "not overweight or overweight" ("underweight or about the right weight" responses were both coded as "not overweight"). Objective weight status of the respondents' child was determined via body mass index (BMI). BMI is an indicator of health, and it is used to screen for weight status. BMI has a number derived from a child's weight and height measurements that indicate a weight status based on normal growth patterns for children of the same age and sex (CDC, 2011; Health Assessment Resource Center, 2011). In the survey, the Health Assessment Resource Center collected the data needed to calculate the BMI status of respondents' children by asking "How tall is your child without shoes?" and "How much does your child weigh without shoes?" (see Appendix). This study selected six predictor variables for sequential binary logistic regression analysis that were chosen in light of the study by Hudson et al. (2012). The six predictor variables were the child's BMI, gender, age, parents' ethnicity (dichotomized White or Hispanic/Latino), and level of education and income. Analysis was performed using IBM SPSS 19.

Results

As illustrated in Table 9, in Block 1, child BMI explained 39% of the variance (Nagelkerke pseudo R^2) in perceptual outcome, and it was statistically significant ($Wald = 47.22, p < 0.0001, OR = 1.351$). In Block 2, child gender and age along with parents' level of education and income were included with no statistical significance (see Table 9). In the final step, birth parents' ethnicity was added to the equation. Child BMI and parent ethnicity together then explained 43% of the variance. Parents' ethnicity accounted for the greatest variance other than BMI ($Wald = 04.53, p = 0.033, OR = 2.87$) as shown in Table 9. Findings indicated that Hispanic/Latinos were nearly 3 times as likely to identify their child as "overweight" compared to Whites.

Results suggest that the child's actual weight status and parents' ethnicity have the greatest influence on parental perception of juvenile weight status. There are some other interesting findings worth reporting even though they did not reach statistical significance. If the child was female, it was somewhat more likely that she would be classified as overweight ($OR = 1.95$). This result concurs with one from Hudson et al. (2012). Also worth noting is, from some exploratory analyses, a rather extreme odds ratio (0.60) indicated that mothers are only two-thirds as likely as fathers to classify their child as overweight.

Discussion

The most significant finding in this study was that Hispanic/Latino parents were nearly 3 times as likely to identify their child as overweight as compared to their White counterparts. The most logical explanation for this would be there were actually 3 times as many overweight Hispanic/Latino children in the sample than overweight White children. Unfortunately, that inference could not be made from this data. However, such a finding would not be unexpected: Trends have been identified showing an obesity disparity among Mexican Americans and their children (CDC, 2010; Flegal, Carroll, Ogden, & Johnson, 2002; Kimbro, Brooks-Gunn, & McLanahan, 2007; Pan et al., 2009).

Statistics report Whites to have the lowest rate of obesity as compared to Hispanic/Latinos (CDC, 2010; Flegal et al., 2002; Kimbro et al., 2007; Pan et al., 2009). In light of these facts, it is also possible that Hispanic/Latino parents in this study area are aware of this unhealthy weight disparity and as a result were more critical about their weights than Whites were. Indeed, there is some evidence that perceptions of appropriate weight differ among Mexican American mothers in California and those in Mexico. Rosas et al. (2009) conducted a study comparing the maternal perception of child weight among Mexicans in California (Salinas Valley California) and those in Mexico

Table 1 <i>Child Characteristics Summarized (n = 293)</i>			Table 2 <i>Respondent Characteristics Summarized (n = 293)</i>		
	<i>Child BMI</i>	<i>Child Age</i>		<i>Respondent Education</i>	<i>Income</i>
Mean	20.5261	10.4232	Mean	2.79	9.3174
Mode	15.26	15.00	Mode	4	20.00
Std. Deviation	5.23950	4.66021	Std. Deviation	1.272	6.20249
Minimum	6.83	1.00	Minimum	1	1.00
Maximum	37.97	17.00	Maximum	5	20.00
<i>Note.</i> The data in Table 2 corresponds with the numbered rows in Tables 5 and 7.					

Table 3 <i>Parent's Perception of Child's Weight Dichotomized (n - 293)</i>				
<i>Perception</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Valid Percent</i>	<i>Cumulative Percent</i>
Not Overweight	248	84.6	84.6	84.6
Overweight	45	15.4	15.4	100.0

Note. "Underweight" or "about the right weight" combined=Not Overweight

Table 4 <i>Respondent Ethnicity Characteristics (n = 293)</i>				
<i>Ethnicity</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Valid Percent</i>	<i>Cumulative Percent</i>
White	131	44.7	44.7	44.7
Hispanic/Latino	162	55.3	55.3	100.0
Total	293	100.0	100.0	

Table 5 <i>Respondent Education Characteristics (n = 293)</i>				
<i>Education Level</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Valid Percent</i>	<i>Cumulative Percent</i>
1-Less than HS	59	20.1	20.1	20.1
2-HS or GED	70	23.9	23.9	44.0
3-Some college	63	21.5	21.5	65.5
4-College	75	25.6	25.6	91.1
5-Post graduate	26	8.9	8.9	100.0
Total	293	100.0	100.0	

Table 6

Child Gender Characteristics (n = 293)

<i>Gender</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Valid Percent</i>	<i>Cumulative Percent</i>
Male	173	59.0	59.0	59.0
Female	120	41.0	41.0	100.0
Total	293	100.0	100.0	

Table 7

Respondent Income Characteristics (n = 293)

<i>Income</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Valid Percent</i>	<i>Cumulative Percent</i>
01-Less than \$10,000	17	5.8	5.8	5.8
02-\$10,000 to less than \$15,000	15	5.1	5.1	10.9
03-\$15,000 to less than \$20,000	27	9.2	9.2	20.1
04-\$20,000 to less than \$25,000	16	5.5	5.5	25.6
05-\$25,000 to less than \$30,000	24	8.2	8.2	33.8
06-\$30,000 to less than \$35,000	26	8.9	8.9	42.7
07-\$35,000 to less than \$40,000	22	7.5	7.5	50.2
08-\$40,000 to less than \$45,000	16	5.5	5.5	55.6
09-\$45,000 to less than \$50,000	17	5.8	5.8	61.4
10-\$50,000 to less than \$55,000	11	3.8	3.8	65.2
11-\$55,000 to less than \$60,000	8	2.7	2.7	67.9
12-\$60,000 to less than \$65,000	5	1.7	1.7	69.6
13-\$65,000 to less than \$70,000	12	4.1	4.1	73.7
14-\$70,000 to less than \$75,000	5	1.7	1.7	75.4
15-\$75,000 to less than \$80,000	6	2.0	2.0	77.5
16-\$80,000 to less than \$85,000	9	3.1	3.1	80.5
17-\$85,000 to less than \$90,000	5	1.7	1.7	82.3
18-\$90,000 to less than \$95,000	4	1.4	1.4	83.6
19-\$95,000 to less than \$100,000	8	2.7	2.7	86.3
20-\$10,000 or more	40	13.7	13.7	100.0
Total	293	100.0	100.0	

Table 8

Child Age Characteristics (n = 293)

<i>Years of/age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Valid Percent</i>	<i>Cumulative Percent</i>
1	5	1.7	1.7	1.7
2	14	4.8	4.8	6.5
3	8	2.7	2.7	9.2
4	15	5.1	5.1	14.3
5	12	4.1	4.1	18.4
6	14	4.8	4.8	23.2
7	20	6.8	6.8	30.0
8	20	6.8	6.8	36.9
9	14	4.8	4.8	41.6
10	17	5.8	5.8	47.4
11	14	4.8	4.8	52.2
12	21	7.2	7.2	59.4
13	21	7.2	7.2	66.6
14	24	8.2	8.2	74.7
15	27	9.2	9.2	84.0
16	22	7.5	7.5	91.5
17	25	8.5	8.5	100.0
Total	293	100.0	100.0	

(Guanajuato, Jalisco, and Michoacan) and found that mothers in California preferred figures smaller than the larger body-sizes preferred by mothers in Mexico. This could be the result of acculturation and/or perhaps awareness of an unhealthy weight disparity. Regardless, future studies should be vigilant to catalog and observe the results of child BMI status by child ethnicity.

Parents' ethnicity and the child's actual weight proved to be significant factors in this study, yet other variables did not. In contemplating the results, it is important to note that this study was not investigating the causes of obesity but instead perceptions of weight status. Whereas income and education might be contributors to a person's actual weight status, in this study, they did not influence the perceptual weight status of children among parents. This study investigated socio-demographic and anthropometric factors that influence parents' perceptions of

their child's weight status and identifies some correlated influences; however, these findings should be viewed in light of experimental limitations.

Although attempted, it was not possible to link the adult questioner to the child questioner, so birth parents' BMIs could not be included as a predictor variable. Analysis including parents' BMIs as a predictor would be a valuable contribution to the body of knowledge on this topic with regard to identifying to what variance parents' own weight statuses effects their perception of their child's. Another obvious limitation is how child BMI data was collected. The BMI status of a child was calculated via the parents' reports of their child's height and weight; however, since the literature suggests that parents cannot accurately identify their child's weight status, (Health Assessment Resource Center, 2011; Hernandez, 2005; Hernandez et al., 2010; Hudson, McGloin,

Table 9

Results for Each Predicting Factor Respectively by Regression Model Step

Predictor	β	Wald	df	P	OR	R ²
<u>Model 1</u>						
Child's BMI	0.301***	47.219	1	0.000	1.351	0.388
<u>Model 2</u>						
Child's BMI	0.288***	38.844		0.000	1.334	0.410
Child's gender	0.518	1.709		0.191	1.679	
Child's age	0.053	1.157		0.282	1.054	
Parents' level of education	0.238	1.638		0.201	1.268	
Parents' income	-.067	2,256		0.133	0.935	
<u>Model 3</u>						
Child's BMI	0.301***	39.755	1	0.000	1.351	0.432
Child's gender	0.650	2.541	1	0.111	1.915	
Child's age	0.058	1.327		0.249	1.059	
Parents' level of education	0.356	3.322	1	0.068	1.428	
Parents' income	-.050	1.211	1	0.271	0.951	
Parents' ethnicity	1.054*	4.535	1	0.033	2.868	

Note. $n = 293$. Confidence level = 95%. β = standardized coefficients, $Wald$ = wald statistic, df = degrees of freedom, p = statistical significance, OR = odds ratio, R^2 = Nagelkerke pseudo coefficient of determination.

a. * $p < 0.05$. ** $p < 0.01$. *** $p < 0.001$.

b. Step 1 $R^2 = 0.388$, Step 2 $\Delta R^2 = 0.022$, Step 3 $\Delta R^2 = 0.022$.

McConnon, 2011; Parry et al., 2008; Vuorela et al., 2010), the validity of these anthropometric reports is questionable. A health professional assessing the weights of participants' children would be a less biased and more valid method of measurement due to professional training and use of unbiased instrumentation.

The sample of races/ethnicities other than Hispanic/Latinos and Whites were too small to include in this analysis; therefore, future studies should seek to collect a more diverse sample. Only the perceptions of biological parents were included in this study. Future studies might compare perception differences between non-biological guardians and those of birth parents. Last, this study only examined some influences on parents' perception outcome of their child's weight status but not the accuracy of those perceptions. Future studies on this subject should examine correct and incorrect classification of parental perceptions.

Conclusion

In light of the stated weight misperceptions, interventions should take caution to ensure that dependency on parents' weight-related judgments is not crucial to programming. Furthermore, there might be a need to provide families with unbiased instrumentation to monitor their

health-related parenting decisions, such as a bioelectrical impedance. Because ethnicity was found to be a significant predictor, program designs should be culturally appropriate and sensitive. With the increasing cultural diversity of southern California, there is a need for program designs to take a multicultural approach. It cannot be assumed that interventions will have an equal impact on all community members without culturally tailoring approaches with regard to ethnic variation.

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Appendix

Technical Terminology Explained

Weight status refers to a person's weight as *overweight*, *healthy weight*, or *underweight*. Anthropometric measurement refers to measurements of the human body, in this case, adipose (fat) tissue. Body mass index (BMI) is an indicator of health, and it is used to screen for weight status. BMI measurement takes age and gender into account and can identify unhealthy weight problems such as obesity. It is considered a dependable assessment of adipose tissue (CDC, 2011; Health Assessment Resource Center. (2011)). BMI has a number derived from a child's weight and height

measurements. The formula used to find this number is $\text{weight (kg)} / [\text{height (m)}]^2$ or $\text{weight (lb)} / [\text{height (in)}]^2 \times 703$. The product BMI number falls into four different BMI-for-age percentiles: underweight < 5th percentile; healthy weight = 5th percentile to 85th percentile;

overweight = 85th to 95th percentile; and obese > 95th percentile (CDC, 2011). BMI-for-age percentiles are based on normal growth patterns for children and teens by specialist advisement (CDC, 2011; see Figures 1 and 2).

Figure 1 Body Mass Index-for-age Percentiles: Boys, 2 to 20 Years: BMI numbers interpretation for a 10-year-old boy

Source: Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2009). How is BMI calculated and interpreted for children and teens?

http://www.cdc.gov/healthyweight/assessing/bmi/childrens_bmi/about_childrens_bmi.html

Figure 2 Body Mass Index-for-age Percentiles Boys: 2 to 20 Years, BMI numbers interpretation 14-year-old boy and a 15-year-old boy who both have a BMI-for-age of 23. (Note that the two children of different ages are plotted on the same growth chart to illustrate a point. Normally the measurement for only one child is plotted on a growth chart.)

Source: Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2009). How is BMI calculated and interpreted for children and teens?

http://www.cdc.gov/healthyweight/assessing/bmi/childrens_bmi/about_childrens_bmi.html